

DEVELOPMENT OF THE INTELLECTUAL AREA OF STUDENTS - AS A PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM

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Abstract. *This article presents a logical thought about intelligence and its essence, intellectual and creative activity, metacognitive experience, formation and management of intellectual activity, and also analyzes some pedagogical problems that should be paid attention to in this regard.*

Keywords: *intelligence, intellectual activity, creative activity, metacognition, intellectual culture, intellectual initiative, thinking, theoretical thinking, educational process, educational activity.*

Intellect is a Latin word that means to understand, to comprehend, to imagine, to know. On the other hand, intelligence means understanding, judgment, thought, essence. In the encyclopedia of pedagogy, intelligence (Latin intellectus - intelligence, perception, mind) - 1. In a broad sense; activity based on a person's complete knowledge of the essence of an event and manifested through it; in a narrow sense: human thinking, thinking potential. 2. Human mental abilities; the ability to accurately reflect and change life, the environment in consciousness, thinking, reading and learning, knowing the world and accepting social experience; this also means the ability to solve various problems, come to a decision, act rationally, foresee events [1].

Intelligence is the activity of understanding and cognition of a person, the operations of thought, the ability of the brain to know through thinking. If thinking is expressed in concepts, judgments about the external and internal world, categories, then intelligence is an understanding of the world through concepts. These concepts allow us to express objects through words. This is not an emotional, but an intellectual apparatus of human activity.

From a psychological point of view, the essence of intelligence is the ability to create an ordered activity aimed at eliminating chaos, based on the individual needs of a person, based on the objective requirements of reality. This is a subjective view of reality in a person's life, provided by mental mechanisms. This is an activity that allows you to perform actions that correspond to reality. In general, intelligence is a form of individual human mental experience, and the mental field that is born with it consists of a mental representation of reality that is realized within this field. In a word, intelligence is an existing mental structure of a person, a space of mental reflection created by him and a form of emergence and manifestation of individual mental experience as mental images of events occurring in this space. These ideas can be appropriately considered as a scientific model of intelligence. This is a form of human representation of reality in a mutually compatible form, ensuring conscious implementation of actions. It helps to bring this reality into line with the ways of changing it. The study of the problem of intelligence and attempts to formulate it show that there is a need to measure it. There is a growing need to develop methods for determining the level of human intelligence. The analysis of personal intelligence and creative activity was carried out by famous psychologists M.A. Kholodny, D.B. Bogoyavlenskaya. The analysis carried out by experts created a basis for promoting critical approaches. The critical aspects identified by the experts are expressed in the following:

1. The results of measuring a person's intelligence quotient do not reflect a person's intellectual achievements and do not allow one to comprehend these achievements. This is especially noticeable in the context of educational activities.

2. There is no direct connection between the educational abilities of students and an increase in IQ.

3. In addition, it is based on the fact that the IQ changes throughout a person's life, which allows us to demonstrate the growth of students' intellectual abilities.

4. Students who make decisions quickly make more mistakes than students who tend to react and make decisions slowly. That is why the intelligence of students who make decisions slowly is considered productive.

In this regard, experts emphasized that in diagnosing students' intellectual abilities, the cognitive mechanisms that create this product are important, rather than a description of the final result. (M. A. Kholodnaya) Students' metacognitive experiences play a major role here. Because metacognitive skills serve to ensure students' personal activity. In this place, students' voluntary intellectual control, metacognitive awareness, and open knowledge occupy a special place.

Mathematical cognitive awareness refers to ideas about the construction of scientific knowledge and methods for the effective use of these ideas. These mechanisms serve to develop students' activities in the intellectual implementation of their activities, the acquisition of skills for free management of them, the organization of independent learning and learning processes. Specific features of the development of the intellectual sphere of students include the formation of a culture inherent in their internal processes, the creation of conditions for the regular birth of new ideas, and ensuring the intellectual development of students. That is why it is necessary to think first of all about the development of intellectual culture in students. Because on the basis of intellectual culture, it is possible to develop the intellectual activity of students. Intellectual activity encourages a person to regularly learn about events that are important to him.

Views on the nature of intelligence should be explained based on the analysis of all its cognitive mechanisms. Because the effectiveness of intellectual activity is considered based on the analysis of cognitive mechanisms. Accordingly, by measuring and evaluating the mental mechanisms of a student, it becomes possible to manage his intellectual activity. Each person should be able to manage his intellectual activity.

From particular importance in the formation and management of intellectual activity is the use of creative space, this idea was put forward by D. B. Bogoyavlensky. As a result of studying the nature of intellectual initiative, it should be noted that it is interpreted as the ability to independently develop an activity. According to A. M. Kondakova and A. A. Kuznetsova, the first layer of this method is assessed by students as an instrumental resource. The scope of the second layer includes an external, non-directed form of intellectual activity. Students do not know about it, but the need to know attracts them to intellectual activity. Until recently, there was no instrument for measuring students' intellectual abilities, so no attention was paid to the use of technologies for developing students' intellectual spheres.

Intelligence and its mechanisms develop in the process of acquiring knowledge. Intellectual activity occurs when students have an idea of certain things, when their logical memory organizes and popularizes the acquired knowledge as a separate cognitive process. When the instrumental support of educational mechanisms is implemented in the pedagogical process, the opportunity for intellectual development of students appears. This requires the development of

mechanisms for the acquisition, implementation and application of knowledge by students. The educational process is aimed at developing competence and competency in students by providing them with knowledge, skills and abilities. However, this process is mainly carried out within the framework of practical thinking, that is, the students' thought process is the course of practical activity. Unlike theoretical thinking, which is aimed at solving theoretical problems, practical thinking serves to solve practical problems. This process does not aim to create new methodological tools.

One of the important tasks of the educational process is to form the experience of intellectual activity by developing the theoretical thinking of students. As a result of the educational process based on practical thinking, its main components are unclear, and there will be no opportunity to present knowledge. They consist of: the process of presentation itself, its level and quality of comprehensibility for speakers, the quality of assimilation and perception of knowledge by students.

Productive thinking of students allows them to creatively complete tasks. Such tasks will consist of a set of tasks for students with new, non-standard solutions of an intellectual nature. It should be noted that creative execution of tasks is also characteristic of practical thinking. Creative activity in students does not just arise. It becomes a reality when in the process of creative activity it is possible to create a specific product. The product of creative activity is formed and presented to others with deep understanding. These skills are formed as a result of educational activity in the educational process. For this, it is necessary to develop a methodology for choosing pedagogical means of a new nature, since this methodology creates a new, productive situation in the educational process. Accordingly, as a result of developing the intellectual sphere of students, it is possible to create a mutually compatible internal culture in them. To do this, it is necessary to develop productive thinking in students during the educational process. It is important that this is based on the individual content of the student. In order to form such thinking in students, it is necessary to theoretically substantiate the pedagogical essence of this problem. Theoretical substantiation of the general patterns and signs of this phenomenon allows us to present the essence of the problem more broadly. To do this, it is necessary to ensure communication between the subjects of the pedagogical process. This process covers the process from didactic goals to the acquisition by students of the skills, qualifications and competencies necessary for mastering knowledge, their control and assessment.

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